

A block chain-based E-commerce reputation system built with verifiable credentials

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KEYWORDS

Hyperledger Indy,
Hyperledger Fabric,
Verifiable Credentials,
Digital Identity Management

ABSTRACT

Reviews and reputation scores of sellers play an important role in decision-making process of potential buyers in an e-commerce system. A trust worthy and reliable reputation system is a crucial component in the e-commerce ecosystem, as buyer rely on it to make informed decisions. In this work, we propose a privacy-preserving decentralized reputation system designed to include countermeasures against some known attacks. Our model is built on two permission block chains, namely Hyper ledger Indy and Hyper ledger Fabric. Hyper ledger Indy provides an infrastructure for implementing verifiable credentials with zero knowledge proof support, which is essential for privacy preservation, while hyper ledger Fabric is a robust platform for identity of sellers, feedback tokens issued to buyer after performing an e-commerce transaction and discount tokens issued to buyers after feedback submission. This helps to ensure that the feedback and identity information is authentic and tamper-proof, reducing the likelihood of identity-related attacks. Additionally, the collection of feedbacks and application of business rules are implemented as smart contracts on Hyper ledger Fabric block chain. This provides a secure and transparent mechanism for processing feedback, reducing the likelihood of unfair feedbacks. Overall, the proposed approach presents a robust reputation system that help reduce identity-related attacks and unfair feedbacks. The privacy-preserving nature of the system ensures that sensitive information is protected while still enabling the verification of digital identities. The use of feedback and discount tokens incentivizes buyers to provide accurate and honest feedback, which can help reduce unfair feedbacks and identity related attacks. Finally, the use of smart contracts ensures transparency and immutability, which enhances the overall reliability of the system..

1. INTRODUCTION

The volume of the e-commerce market has rapidly increased in the recent years, especially with the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. Accordingly, the need for a reliable and satisfactory e-commerce experience for the buyers has become more and more important. Many factors affect the buying decisions, including quality and price of a product together with the reputation of a seller. Among these, reputation of a seller is built by the cumulative purchasing experiences of the buyers. Reviews and ratings of the buyers form the reputation of the sellers. The formation of reputations helps the prospective buyers decide whether to take part in an e-commerce transaction with a seller or not. This form of transitive trust was formulated as Eigen Trust algorithm for reputation management in P2P networks by Kamvar et al [1]. Many e-commerce sites provide means for buyers to submit reviews and ratings for sellers after completing the shopping. These reviews and ratings are collected and processed by the reputation system of that e-commerce site and a reputation score is calculated per seller. The reviews and reputation scores give buyers some degree of trust about sellers although buyers do not usually know sellers. However, there are many possible or encountered attacks against the reputation systems, which would reduce the trust worthiness of these systems. Koutrouli et al. had a thorough survey on these attacks and produced taxonomy of the attacks [2]. This taxonomy includes three main categories: unfair recommendations, inconsistent behavior and identity management related attacks [2]. However, not all of the attacks classified in these categories are applicable to the topic of this article. The following is the list of attacks that are relevant for an e-commerce reputation system where only buyers send feedbacks for sellers. Bad-mouthing/Slandering attack is a kind of unfair recommendations attack where an attacker provides false negative feedback about sellers in order to degrade their reputation. This attack is mostly expected to come from a competitor. Ballot-stuffing / Self-Promotion attack is the opposite of bad-mouthing or slandering attack. In this attack, the aim is to increase the reputation score of a seller by injecting false positive feedbacks to the system. As indicated by Hasan et al., this attack can be performed by two users by repeatedly transacting with each other and then assigning each other positive

feedback [3]. White washing / Re-entry attack is an identity management related attack. A seller with a bad reputation exits the system and re-joins using a new identity to start with a fresh reputation. The system is vulnerable to this kind of attack when there is no way of linking the identity of the old seller with the new one. Sybil attackers create multiple identities in the system so that they can have more influence on the reputation scores. Attackers with multiple identities may use this advantage either for bad-mouthing or for ballot-stuffing. Traitors/Oscillation attacker may behave properly for some time to be a trusted party, and then later on start deceiving. This has been encountered in eBay, where sellers build trust by participating in many transactions with small amounts, and then cheat buyers on high-priced items.

In traditional e-commerce systems, reputation is typically managed by centralized platforms that collect and store data on sellers. However, this approach has several limitations, such as vulnerability to manipulation, lack of transparency, and difficulty in sharing reputation data across multiple platforms. Block chain technology provides a decentralized and tamper-proof way of managing reputation data, which is transparent, immutable, and can be shared across multiple platforms. This means that sellers can build a trusted reputation profile that can be used across multiple e-commerce platforms, making it easier to establish trust and conduct transactions securely and efficiently. On the other hand, nonblock chain-based reputation systems are centralized, meaning that the reputation data is controlled by a single entity, such as an e-commerce platform, which can be vulnerable to manipulation and censorship. This research aims to create measures to tackle with the known attacks against reputation systems by modeling a block chain-based decentralized reputation system. Our model uses block chain technology not only for submissions and storing the feedbacks but also for issuing and verification of verifiable credentials.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Because of the decentralized and immutable nature of the blockchain technology, there have been many researches on using blockchain in reputation systems in the recent years.

A.E-COMMERCEREPUTATIONSYSTEMS BASEDON PUBLIC BLOCKCHAINS

There are many researches proposing decentralized block chain-based reputation systems built on public block chains and crypto currencies, such as Bitcoin and Ethereum. Some of these systems focus on preserving the privacy of reviewers. Sun et al. aimed to prevent some types of attacks by spending "reputation tokens" for sending review scores, which would have a weight proportional to the tokens spent [5]. Nodes are supposed to earn tokens as long as they create block in the blockchain network. They claimed that this model would preserve the privacy of the reviewer. However, there are no incentives for the reviewers to gain more tokens and to provide reviews. Schaub et al. proposed a more comprehensive privacy preserving reputation system to prevent some types of attacks [6]. The main component of their model is the blinded token issued by the service provider to the buyer to let the buyer submit feedback. Service provider needs to earn and spend coins of the underlying blockchain in order to be able to issue tokens. Owino et al. also proposed a model which is very similar to the one proposed by Schaub et al [7]. However, it is not clear how service providers are supposed to earn coins and ensure that they have enough coins to issue tokens to buyers in both models. Carboni proposed a Bitcoin based reputation system, which depends on Bitcoin payments [11]. Bitcoin addresses are used for preserving privacy of reviewers. Soska et al. proposed a reputation system coupled with a decentralized marketplace called Beaver [16]. Although the proposed solution seems promising against reputation system attacks, it is totally built on decentralized marketplace architecture and cryptocurrency-based payments. On the other hand, some systems do not focus on preserving the privacy of reviewers. Most of these reputation systems are based on Ethereum blockchain. Tamang calculated "Total Endorsement Impact" score in order to prevent some attacks in his model, which is based on Ethereum, a public permissionless blockchain network [8]. Calculation of this score is based on both incoming and outgoing connections of endorsers and endorsees, which may result in unexpected reputation scores for an e-commerce system. Another Ethereum based reputation system is proposed by Dhakal et al., which they named as DTrust [9]. The limitations of DTrust is that it depends

on the payments performed on Ethereum and it does not consider preserving privacy of reviewers. Zulfiqar et al. also proposed an Ethereum based reputation system with similar constraints, which they named as EthReview [10]. Wang et al. also proposed an Ethereum based reputation system named ReviewChain [13]. Review Chain is designed not for e-commerce applications but for supply chain systems built on blockchain. Almasoud also proposed an Ethereum based reputation system for e-commerce marketplaces in his thesis [14]. His model embeds review phase as an inseparable part of e-commerce session and does not consider preserving the privacy of reviewers. There are also other non-privacy preserving reputation systems based on public blockchain networks other than Ethereum. Ahn et al. proposed a reputation system built on Bitcoin crypto currency-based payment systems by storing the transactions and the user reviews on the block chain ledger [4]. The limitation of this system is its dependency on the crypto currency-based payment system. Buechler et al. also proposed a decentralized reputation system built on Bitcoin network and Ethereum smart contracts, which calculates reputation score with their proprietary reputation algorithm [12]. Ramachandran proposed two block chains in his model, one for storing review records and the other for storing buyers and sellers [15]. The second block chain also keeps records of purchases in conjunction with the buyer and seller records. The redundant storage of information brings an additional cost of synchronization of the records since e-commerce platforms already maintain these records. In addition, privacy of the buyers are not preserved since they are kept with their basic information.

B.E-COMMERCEREPUTATION SYSTEMS BASEDON PERMISSIONED BLOCKCHAINS

The decentralized reputation system proposed by Kugblenu and Vuorimaa is one of the very few permissions block chain-based reputation systems [21]. It tries to preserve privacy by generating review token at checkout step, which is only a concatenated text composed of ProductID, RetailerID and OrderID. However, there is no signature and cryptographic validation of the token during review submission. Another permissioned block chain-based reputation system proposal is RepChain, which is an anonymous and verifiable reputation system for e-Commerce

platforms [40]. RepChain uses blind signatures for preserving privacy of reviewers.

C. OTHER REPUTATION SYSTEMS BASED ON PUBLIC BLOCK CHAINS

There are some other researches related with decentralized reputation systems focusing on areas other than e-commerce. Mendes et al. built a reputation system on blockchain for storing reviews of mobile applications on application stores and processed these reviews on cloud-based systems [17]. Although it looks similar, there are many different characteristics of mobile application reviews and e-commerce reviews. Another application of a decentralized reputation system is proposed for auctions by Omori and Kishigami [18]. Their work is based on Ethereum blockchain; but dedicated to reputations of sellers in auctions. Park et al. proposed a smart-contract based decentralized review system for IoT data marketplaces [19]. Nguyen et al. proposes a block chain-based trust model for evaluating the trustworthiness of reviews from the crowd, such as social media.

3. EXISTINGSYSTEM

Sun et al. aimed to prevent some types of attacks by spending "reputation tokens" for sending review scores, which would have a weight proportional to the tokens' spent Nodes are supposed to earn tokens as long as they create block in the block chain network. They claimed that this model would preserve the privacy of the reviewer. However, there are no incentives for the reviewers to gain more tokens and to provide reviews. Schaub et al. proposed a more comprehensive privacy preserving reputation system to prevent some types of attacks. The main component of their model is the blinded token issued by the service provider to the buyer to let the buyer submit feedback. Service provider needs to earn and spend coins of the underlying block chain in order to be able to issue tokens. However, it is not clear how service providers are supposed to earn coins and ensure that they have enough coins to issue tokens to buyers in both models. Carboniproposed a Bit coin-based reputation system, which depends on Bit coinpayments. Bit coin addresses are used for preserving privacy of reviewers. Soska et al. proposed a reputation system coupled with a decentralized marketplace called Beaver. Although the proposed solution seems promising against reputation system attacks, it is totally

built on decentralized marketplace architecture and crypto currency-based payments.

4. PROPOSEDSYSTEM

Our work proposes a decentralized reputation system that utilizes verifiable credentials to ensure security and privacy. Verifiable credentials are used as:

- 1) Feedback tokens for buyers, ensuring that only those who have completed a shopping transaction can submit reviews and ratings
- 2) Digital identities of sellers to provide uniqueness for the complete legal lifetime of the seller and on all the e-commerce platforms
- 3) Discount tokens issued to reviewers as an incentive mechanism for feedback submission. E-commerce platforms in the system can accept these tokens to provide discounts or any other kinds of special offers to reviewers.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

5. UML DIAGRAMS

1. CLASS DIAGRAM

The cornerstone of event-driven data exploration is the class outline. Both broad practical verification of the application's precision and fine-grained demonstration of the model translation into software code rely on its availability. Class graphs are another data visualization option.

The core components, application involvement, and class changes are all represented by comparable classes in the class diagram. Classes with three-participant

boxes are referred to be "incorporated into the framework," and each class has three different locations:

- The techniques or actions that the class may use or reject are depicted at the bottom.

Fig 5.1 shows the class diagram

2. USECASE DIAGRAM:

A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

Fig 5.2 Shows the Use case Diagram

3. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams, event scenarios, and timing diagrams.

Fig 5.3 Shows the Sequence Diagram

6. RESULTS

6.1 Output Screens

Fig 6.1 Home Page

In above screen shows the home page of the project.

Fig 6.2 Admin Login

In above screen shows the admin login

File Id	Transaction No	Product No	Product Name	Price	Quantity	Customer No	Discount	Taken	Net Cost
A18K100H12MVB	881482	11-Sep-2022	Set of 2 Wooded Market Crates	21.47	12.0	11069.0	588.0	588.0	Units Kango
A2FH12MBAUJA	881475	12-Sep-2022	Whisk List Chalkboard	0.85	36.0	11069.0	1141.0	1141.0	Units Kango
A8HPDEEG68SR	881475	11-Sep-2022	Storage Tin Vintage Leaf	11.53	12.0	11069.0	669.0	669.0	Units Kango
A375ZM4U74979	881475	11-Sep-2022	Tree T Light Holder White Wicker	0.65	12.0	11069.0	1247.0	1247.0	Units Kango
A1DCSC6NVONZ	881475	11-Sep-2022	Set of 4 Knick Knack Tin Poppin	11.94	6.0	11069.0	411.0	411.0	Units Kango
A26YHXZDSUFPVQ	881475	11-Sep-2022	Big Fatg Bowl Marbles	0.85	24.0	11069.0	292.0	292.0	Units Kango
AJCVWZL1USX2B1	881475	12-Sep-2022	Joy Wooded Block Letters	11.23	18.0	11069.0	1134.0	1134.0	Units Kango

Fig 6.3 Block Chain Datasets

In above screen shows the all block chain datasets.

Fig 6.4 Attacks Results

In above screen shows the E-commerce Reputation results.

Fig 6.5 User Home Page

In above screen shows the user home page.

Product ID	Product Name	ECommerce Reputation Type
22485	Set Of 2 Wooden Market Crates	Good
22596	Christmas Star Wash List Chalkboard	Good
23235	Storage Tin Vintage Leaf	Good
23272	Tree T-Light Holder Willie Wonkie	Good
23239	Set Of 4 Knick Knack Tins Poppies	Good
21705	Rag 500g Seirly Marbles	Good
22118	Joy Wooden Block Letters	Good

Fig 6.6 View E-commerce Reputation Type

In above screen shows the E-commerce reputation type.

Fig 6.7 Find E-commerce Reputation Type

In above screen shows the E-commerce Reputation Type.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a mobile crowd sensing framework for dynamic traffic violation hotspot inference and adaptive patrol task scheduling. Specifically, we first extract traffic violation events from heterogeneous crowd-sensed data, and cluster them into traffic violation-prone locations with a road network-based clustering algorithm. Then, we propose a context-aware self-adaptive learning approach to infer traffic violation hotspots. Finally, we find the patrol routes with a maximal coverage ratio of traffic violation hotspots under resource constraints by a proposed tensor-based integer linear programming modeling method. We evaluate our framework using real-world datasets collected from Xiamen and Chengdu. Results show that our framework accurately infers traffic violation hotspots and generates patrol routes adaptively, outperforming the baseline methods. In the future, we intend to improve this work from the following aspects. First, we plan to incorporate traffic accident records, and collect more traffic violation data leveraging crowd sensing platforms. Second, we plan to consider more factors in patrol route optimization, for example, the influence of incentives on patrol participants. Third, we plan to evaluate our framework in more cities with different geographic and meteorological conditions, and explore the similarities and differences of relative spatiotemporal contextual features in different cities.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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